

Implementation of Population Administration Policy at the Integrated Service Unit (UPT) of the Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the implementation of population administration policies at the Integrated Service Unit (UPT) of the Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency. The research uses a descriptive qualitative approach, focusing on George C. Edwards III's public policy implementation theory, which includes communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure. The results indicate that policy implementation has not been optimal, as evidenced by low achievement in population document issuance and various human resource and infrastructure constraints. This study recommends strengthening cross-sector coordination and enhancing the capacity of field technical implementers.

KEYWORDS: Policy Implementation, Population Administration, Population and Civil Registration Office

INTRODUCTION

The urgency of population administration policies in Indonesia continues to rise alongside increasingly complex issues related to population interests. The Indonesian government is thus required to develop programs and activities to address these issues, all of which are encompassed in population administration policies. Population administration plays a vital role in supporting sustainable development. These policies are designed to streamline population administration systems, protect community rights, and ensure legal certainty for citizens and residents [1;2].

Based on Law No. 23 of 2006 on Population Administration, later reinforced by Law No. 24 of 2013 on Amendments to Law No. 23 of 2006, population administration is defined as a series of activities to organize and regulate the issuance of population documents and data through population registration, civil registration, management of population administration information, and its utilization for public services and sectoral development [3;4].

Population administration is a subsystem of public administration, playing a critical role in governance and development. Consequently, population registration and civil registration, as pillars of the population administration system, must be well-organized to contribute to governance and development improvements [5].

Furthermore, Law No. 24 of 2013 stipulates that the implementing agency for population administration at the regency/city level is the Population and Civil Registration Office, authorized to provide services to residents regarding the reporting of vital events and population matters. The Population and Civil Registration Office is responsible for executing population administration tasks under the principles of regional autonomy and co-administration [4].

Overall, population administration policies comprise a set of regulations, procedures, and programs designed to manage population data. These policies aim to facilitate government access to population data, enabling more precise decision-making and policy development [6].

A crucial stage in population administration policy is its implementation as the process of applying these policies in daily practice. Policy implementation is broadly defined as the execution of laws involving all actors, organizations, procedures, and techniques working comprehensively to achieve policy objectives [7].

The implementation of population administration policies in Indonesia refers to the process of executing various government policies to manage population data and documents effectively. This implementation aims to improve public service quality through standardized and computerized systems, making population administration services more accessible to the public [8;9;10;11].

Effective implementation of population administration policies is essential for good governance and sustainable development, as it centralizes and streamlines administrative services. The implementation process involves interconnected administrative activities, requiring careful consideration of strategies, approaches, formulation stages, and administrative completeness [12].

Studies on population administration policy implementation in various regions of Indonesia reveal that centralized administration management is a progressive step in public service provision, facilitating government access to population data for policymaking [6]. Although implementation generally follows established procedures, there remains room for service quality improvement. Challenges include insufficient personnel capable of fully managing the Population Administration Information System (SIAM) database [5]. Effective communication, both internal and external, plays a key role in successful policy implementation at the regency level [5]. This study focuses on the implementation of population administration policies, conceptually grounded in George C. Edwards III's theory [13], which emphasizes that policy implementation is crucial because even the best policies will fail if implementation is not well-prepared and planned. Edwards III's theory identifies four factors determining policy implementation success: 1) Communication, 2) Resources, 3) Disposition, and 4) Bureaucratic structure.

The study examines the implementation of population administration policies at the Integrated Service Unit (UPT) of the Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency, using Edwards III's framework. This framework is chosen because it aligns with the contextual challenges faced in policy implementation at this UPT.

The Banggai Regency Population and Civil Registration Office operates nine Integrated Service Units (UPTs) across 23 subdistricts. This study focuses on the UPT in Bunta Subdistrict, which serves Bunta, Nuhon, and Simpang Raya Subdistricts.

Preliminary observations in May–June 2024 indicate that population administration services at the UPT in Bunta Subdistrict have not achieved 100% targets. For example, only 74% of the 54,100 residents in its coverage area have birth certificates. In Tomeang Village, Nuhon Subdistrict, only 782 out of 2,100 residents possess identity cards (KTP).

These findings suggest suboptimal policy implementation. The UPT's operations are guided by Law No. 24 of 2013 and Central Sulawesi Provincial Regulation No. 5 of 2022.

The 2023 Performance Evaluation Report highlights insufficient policy communication/socialization. Public awareness of the importance of population documents and civil registration remains low (74–86%), with minimal socialization of Law No. 24 of 2013 and Regulation No. 5 of 2022 conducted since 2022 [14].

Human resource support is also suboptimal. The Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) for Bunta Subdistrict's Population Administration Services mandates one front office officer and one operator. However, the front office officer also acts as the operator. Despite SOP requirements for friendly and communicative staff, some operators lack clarity in explaining procedures to the public [14].

Infrastructure limitations further hinder implementation. The SOP requires document printing after approval from the regency office. However, the UPT's printer has been broken for two years, forcing printing to be redirected to Luwuk Subdistrict's UPT [14].

Disposition support is lacking, as internal monitoring mechanisms, such as monthly coordination meetings, are inconsistently conducted [14]. Bureaucratic structure support is also weak, with minimal routine coordination among related offices (village offices, subdistrict offices, and the UPT) [14].

The SOP for Bunta Subdistrict's Population Administration Services derives from Law No. 24 of 2013 and Regulation No. 5 of 2022. The challenges identified in this UPT lie in the policy execution phase, necessitating sustainable improvements.

METHOD

This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach to holistically and contextually describe population administration policy implementation at the UPT in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency. Data were collected through participatory observation, in-depth interviews, and document analysis of policies and administrative reports. Purposive sampling selected 21 informants, including leaders, staff, community members, and stakeholders. Data analysis followed reduction, presentation, and conclusion stages, validated through triangulation and peer review.

RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Communication

The communication aspect in the process of communicating or socializing policies related to the implementation of population administration services at the Integrated Service Unit (UPT) of the Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency, includes the delivery of clear, accurate, and easily understandable information to the public regarding the applicable policies. This process involves government efforts to convey the objectives, procedures, and benefits of population

administration policies, such as the issuance of ID cards, birth certificates, and other documents, through various effective communication media, including direct meetings, pamphlets, social media, and public announcements. The effectiveness of this communication influences public understanding and participation in utilizing the services provided. Proper socialization helps create alignment between government policies and community needs, thereby enhancing the efficiency and quality of local population administration services.

Interview results indicate that information on population administration policies has been conveyed to the public within the working area of the Integrated Service Unit (UPT) of the Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency. This is consistent with research observations that show an information delivery mechanism implemented by the UPT office through social media (WhatsApp). Officers of the UPT Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict also provide direct explanations to citizens visiting the office regarding administrative procedures such as the issuance of electronic ID cards (KTP-el), family cards (KK), birth certificates, and data changes. Furthermore, the UPT collaborates with village officials to disseminate information on population administration to villagers through regular meetings (village deliberations) or health post (posyandu) activities.

However, data from the 2023 Performance Evaluation Document at the UPT Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict show that the communication/socialization process in implementing population administration policy has not been optimal. Socialization of Law No. 24 of 2013 and Regional Regulation No. 5 of 2022 has been insufficient. Since 2022, only one socialization event has been conducted at the Banggai Regency Population and Civil Registration Office [14].

Public understanding of the procedures required to access population administration services at the UPT Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict remains varied. According to research observations, understanding of administrative service procedures (KTP-el, KK, birth certificates, and other documents) differs by age group. People aged 18–35 tend to have better understanding due to their familiarity with information technology and social media, allowing them to access information through digital platforms and visit the UPT office more easily. Individuals aged 36–50 have a moderate understanding but still require assistance with technical steps such as form completion and using online systems. Elderly citizens and those from remote or information-limited areas exhibit low comprehension. They are often confused by frequently changing procedures and need detailed explanations from UPT officers. Past experience with document processing also plays a role in understanding among this group.

According to the 2023 Performance Evaluation Document at the UPT Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, public awareness of the importance of population and civil registration documents remains low, ranging between 74% and 86%.

Coordination is carried out between the UPT Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict and village governments in socializing population administration policies in Bunta, Nuhon, and Simpang Raya Subdistricts. This is supported by research observations indicating that the UPT collaborates with village governments to conduct direct socialization through village deliberations (musdes), posyandu cadre meetings, and religious events. Village governments act as intermediaries between the UPT and the community, conveying policy information received from the UPT. Coordination is facilitated through WhatsApp groups that include UPT officers, village heads, and village apparatus. These groups are used to share the latest information, address challenges, and respond to questions related to population administration services.

Based on research findings, the communication/socialization process of policy implementation in population administration at the UPT Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency, has not been running optimally. Although information about population administration policies has been delivered to the public in Bunta Subdistrict, and coordination between the UPT and village governments exists in policy socialization efforts, public awareness regarding the importance of population documents and civil registration certificates remains low.

B. Resources

Resources in the context of implementing policies on population administration services at the Integrated Service Unit (UPT) of the Population and Civil Registration Office, Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency, refer to all necessities required to implement the policy effectively. Resources serve as a key element in determining whether a policy can be carried out as planned. Resource support for implementing population administration policies in this context includes all forms of resources necessary to ensure smooth policy execution, encompassing human resources, infrastructure and facilities, and financial resources (budget/funding).

Interview results illustrate the availability of human resources at the UPT Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency. However, both quantitatively (number of personnel) and qualitatively (competency), improvements

are still needed to optimally implement population administration policies. This aligns with research observations that the UPT has a limited number of employees, both in technical and administrative roles.

Based on the SOP Document No. 060/29.a/KEC.BUNTA/2024 on Population Administration Service Standards in Bunta Subdistrict, it is stated that there is one front office officer and one operator. However, in practice, the front office officer also doubles as the operator. The SOP further outlines that one of the competencies required of service staff in population administration is to be friendly, polite, and communicative. Nevertheless, it was found that some staff especially the operator still lack communication skills in explaining service procedures that the public finds difficult to understand [14].

Interview results also show the availability of facilities and infrastructure supporting the delivery of population administration services at the UPT Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict. However, the current infrastructure remains limited. According to research observations, there are many constraints related to technological equipment, waiting room facilities, and operational tools. The main problems include outdated technology, worn-out facilities, unstable internet connections, and a lack of operational vehicles.

The SOP Document No. 060/29.a/KEC.BUNTA/2024 also outlines that one procedure involves printing population administration documents such as family cards (KK), once approved by the Disdukcapil. However, in reality, the printing process at the Bunta UPT has not been operational for the past two years due to damaged printing equipment. As a result, printing has been redirected to the UPT office in Luwuk [14].

Interviews reveal that the allocated budget is not yet fully sufficient to support the implementation of population administration policies at the Bunta UPT. Research observations confirm that the budget comes from the Banggai Regency APBD (Regional Budget), channeled through the Population and Civil Registration Office. A small portion of supporting activities is funded through central government programs related to population administration. The annual budget allocation covers several main components, such as office operations (electricity, office supplies, equipment maintenance) and procurement of supporting facilities for document printing. However, the financial support remains limited and inadequate for optimal policy implementation. In the 2024 fiscal year, the allocation amounted to approximately IDR 200,000, mainly used for office operations (supplies, electricity, etc.), technology maintenance, and policy socialization to the public. Nevertheless, it falls short of supporting routine facility maintenance.

Based on the findings, support in terms of human resources, infrastructure, and budget for the implementation of population administration policy at the UPT Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency, is still suboptimal. Key obstacles in this aspect include the limited number of staff and their insufficient competencies, technological limitations due to frequent damage or malfunctions, and inadequate operational budget to meet service needs, facility maintenance, and policy outreach activities.

C. Disposition

Disposition in the context of implementing population administration policies at the Integrated Service Unit (UPT) of the Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency refers to the attitudes, understanding, commitment, and responses of policy implementers in carrying out their duties and responsibilities to achieve policy goals. Dispositional support for the implementation of these policies reflects the commitment, attitude, and willingness of the policy implementers to execute population administration policies effectively and responsibly.

Interview results indicate a strong commitment from the staff at the UPT Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency in implementing population administration policies. This is supported by research observations, which show that employees at the UPT have a good understanding of their roles and responsibilities in implementing population administration tasks, such as electronic ID card (KTP-el) registration, issuance of family cards (KK), birth certificates, and data updates. Most staff members are aware that population administration is a vital basic service for the community.

The interviews also reflect a positive attitude and perception among employees at the UPT toward population administration policies. Research findings support this, indicating that most UPT staff hold a positive outlook on such policies. They perceive the policies as strategic efforts and essential governmental steps to provide legal identity and certainty for every citizen. The employees demonstrate dedication in carrying out the policies despite facing various challenges, such as limited facilities, infrastructure constraints, and high workloads. They remain committed to delivering the best services by optimizing available resources. The staff show proactive attitudes by seeking alternative solutions when internet disruptions occur and are open to public feedback to improve future services.

Additionally, the interviews illustrate the presence of coordination and cooperation among staff in supporting the implementation of population administration policies at the UPT. Research observations show that both leadership and staff at the UPT routinely coordinate with the Banggai Regency Population and Civil Registration Office to report service progress and communicate field challenges. Despite a limited number of personnel, they collaborate to ensure service continuity. Employees assist each other in handling technical issues, such as printer malfunctions. When necessary, they work together to find temporary solutions to avoid service disruptions. Initiatives like using personal equipment or sharing responsibilities reflect a strong sense of solidarity among staff in overcoming obstacles.

Based on the research findings, dispositional support for implementing population administration policies at the UPT in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency is considered strong. This is evidenced by the high level of employee commitment in executing policies, positive attitudes and perceptions toward population administration policies, and the presence of effective coordination and teamwork among staff to support successful policy implementation at the local level.

D. Bureaucratic Structure

The bureaucratic structure in the context of implementing policies on population administration services at the Integrated Service Unit (UPT) of the Population and Civil Registration Office (Disdukcapil), Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency refers to the organizational pattern, hierarchy, division of tasks, and coordination mechanisms used to execute the policy. Bureaucratic support for the implementation of these policies entails the organizational framework, work mechanisms, authority hierarchy, and coordination processes that facilitate smooth and effective policy execution. The structure determines how responsibilities, authority, and tasks in population administration are distributed, implemented, and supervised.

Interview findings indicate that the division of tasks and authority at the UPT in Bunta Subdistrict is aligned with a bureaucratic structure that supports the implementation of population administration policies. Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) are applied in the execution of these policies. Research observations affirm that the SOPs are available and implemented as guidelines at the UPT, specifically SOP Number: 060/29.a/KEC.BUNTA/2024 on Population Administration Service Standards. These SOPs are posted in printed form on the UPT office bulletin board and can be accessed by both staff and the public.

The interview results also highlight the existence of internal monitoring and evaluation mechanisms at the UPT in Bunta Subdistrict to ensure that policy implementation adheres to regulations. Research observations confirm that the Head of the UPT acts as the main supervisor by conducting regular oversight to ensure that all staff perform their duties according to the SOPs. Daily supervision includes direct monitoring at service counters to check staff attendance, document completeness, and service delivery processes. The Head of the UPT periodically checks data input reports in the Population Administration Information System (SIAM) to verify the accuracy and integrity of data. Employees are required to report daily progress and any service-related challenges. Evaluation is conducted based on individual performance, including service completion timeliness and responsiveness to public complaints. A suggestion and complaint box is provided in the service area to assess public satisfaction. Complaints are followed up through internal meetings to identify solutions and prevent recurrence of problems.

Monthly evaluations are carried out through meetings chaired by the Head of the UPT and attended by all employees. The evaluation agenda includes: (1) Service volume recap (e-KTP recording, family card issuance, birth certificates, and other services); (2) Analysis of challenges faced by staff in policy implementation; and (3) Discussion of solutions to improve service quality. The UPT regularly reports its activities to the Banggai Regency Population and Civil Registration Office. Reports include: (1) The number of population documents issued; (2) Technical and administrative problems encountered in the field; and (3) Recommendations for service optimization.

Based on the research findings, bureaucratic structure support for the implementation of population administration policy at the UPT in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency, is considered effective. This is demonstrated by the appropriate distribution of tasks and authority in line with the organizational structure, the implementation of SOPs for carrying out administrative policies, and the existence of internal supervision and evaluation mechanisms at the UPT to ensure that policies are implemented according to established procedures.

DISCUSSION

A. Communication

This research found that the communication or socialization process in the implementation of population administration policy at the Integrated Service Unit (UPT) of the Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency has not yet been optimal. Although information about the population administration policy has been conveyed to the community in Bunta, and coordination between the UPT and village governments in policy socialization exists, public awareness of the importance of civil registration documents remains low. This can be directly linked to Edward III's Policy Implementation Theory [15], which emphasizes that communication is a key factor influencing the success of policy implementation.

Findings Related to Communication Factors in Edward III's Theory

Edward III asserts that successful policy implementation greatly depends on the clarity, consistency, and accuracy of communication to policy recipients. In terms of information clarity, while policy information has been delivered, the low public awareness indicates that the message may not have been fully clear or well understood by the community. This may stem from communication methods that are not well suited to the demographic and educational characteristics of the service area.

Given this situation, consistency in communication is needed in the policy communication/socialization process for population administration implementation at the UPT in Bunta Subdistrict. Socialization should be conducted continuously and consistently so that the message can be well understood and accepted by the public. Sporadic or non-intensive communication will result in low awareness and acceptance of the policy. Although coordination exists between the UPT and village governments, the communication channels used are not sufficiently effective. Consistent with Mozin [16], effective communication requires vertical communication (with the district office) and horizontal communication (among internal staff) to support collaborative implementation. Therefore, policy communication should utilize appropriate channels, such as community leaders, local media, or direct village-level activities, to ensure the information reaches the broader public.

Based on Edward III's theory, weaknesses in the communication process in Bunta's UPT include: information not fully understood, lack of consistent socialization, and ineffective communication channels. To ensure policy implementation succeeds, improvements in communication strategies are required, such as using simpler language, involving local leaders or informal figures in outreach, and utilizing community-based communication tools like village meetings or direct counseling. These improvements would help optimize communication—one of Edward III's key implementation factors—and increase public awareness of the importance of population administration.

Findings in Line with Other Policy Implementation Theories

These findings also align with the theory of Mazmanian and Sabatier [17], who emphasize the importance of clear and consistent communication between policymakers, implementers, and recipients in successful policy implementation. The communication factor in this theory relates to the clarity of policy goals, instructions, and feedback between involved parties. Poor communication may lead to misinterpretation of policy objectives, hindering implementation. Therefore, the UPT in Bunta should conduct policy socialization for all relevant stakeholders—policymakers, implementers, and the public—using simple, understandable language tailored to local contexts.

Furthermore, these findings correspond with Van Meter and Van Horn's theory [18], which states that policy implementation success is influenced by communication between actors and organizations. They stress the importance of information consistency and coordination among implementing institutions to ensure shared understanding of policy goals. Accordingly, the UPT in Bunta should build a two-way communication system that enables both implementers and recipients to provide feedback—such as discussion forums, complaint hotlines, or transparent digital systems.

The findings also reflect Grindle's theory [19], which states that effective communication is part of the contextual variables of policy implementation. Grindle argues that policies are easier to implement when there is effective information dissemination, clear instructions, and strong interaction between policymakers and implementers. Based on this, the UPT should prepare technical guidelines outlining detailed implementation steps, roles and responsibilities, and success indicators.

Lastly, these results are consistent with the theory of Pressman and Wildavsky, which identifies coordination and communication as main factors for successful policy implementation. They explain that policy failure often stems from disrupted communication, miscommunication among responsible parties, or unclear instructions. Thus, the UPT in Bunta should conduct regular evaluations to ensure effective communication. If communication barriers are found, immediate improvements should be made.

By carrying out these steps, the UPT of the Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict can enhance the quality of policy implementation and deliver optimal public services. This will ensure that policy implementation proceeds as planned and provides maximum benefit to the community.

B. Resources

This study found that the support in terms of human resources, facilities and infrastructure, and budget for the implementation of population administration policy at the Integrated Service Unit (UPT) of the Population and Civil Registration Office, Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency, remains suboptimal. The main barriers in this aspect include a limited number of staff and weak staff competencies, inadequate technological infrastructure prone to frequent breakdowns, and insufficient operational budget to meet service needs, facility maintenance, and outreach activities. These issues are directly related to Edward III's Policy Implementation Theory [15], which identifies resources as one of the key factors determining successful policy implementation. Edward III emphasizes that resources include human resources, infrastructure, and sufficient budget to support policy execution.

Human Resources

The study found that the number of personnel is limited and staff competencies are weak. According to Edward III, successful policy implementation requires a sufficient number of staff with technical expertise and the capacity to perform their duties. The researchers argue that the limited number of staff hinders the effectiveness of population administration services. Meanwhile, weak staff competencies reflect a lack of training or capacity building, resulting in substandard performance. Therefore, the UPT in Bunta should increase staffing through recruitment and provide regular training to improve human resource competencies.

Technological Infrastructure

The study also revealed limitations in technological facilities, which are often damaged or malfunctioning. Edward III states that the availability of adequate infrastructure is a crucial prerequisite for policy implementation. Damaged or inadequate facilities will obstruct service operations. According to the researchers, frequent technology failures point to poor maintenance and low-quality equipment, which hampers the smooth running of services. Thus, the UPT should invest in higher-quality technology, conduct regular maintenance, and procure new equipment to support service delivery.

Budget Constraints

Another major finding is the lack of operational budget to meet service delivery needs, facility maintenance, and policy outreach. Edward III highlights that financial support is vital for all aspects of policy implementation. Without sufficient budget, service activities, maintenance, and socialization efforts will be disrupted. The researchers argue that limited funding results in lower service quality, delayed facility repairs, and minimal outreach activities, which reduce public awareness of population administration policies. Therefore, the UPT should allocate adequate funding through effective planning and optimize funding sources.

Theoretical Support and Strategic Recommendations

These findings align with Edward III's theory that underscores the importance of resources in successful policy implementation. Three underperforming resource aspects were identified: the limited number and low competence of personnel, damaged or insufficient technological infrastructure, and lack of budget allocation for operations, maintenance, and outreach. Policy implementation will be more effective if improvements are made in these three areas, such as enhancing staff capacity, acquiring and maintaining infrastructure, and allocating sufficient funding to support population administration services.

The findings also correspond with the theory of Mazmanian and Sabatier [17], which identifies that the capacity of policy implementers significantly influences implementation effectiveness. This capacity includes sufficient funding, adequate staffing, technical skills, and access to supporting information. Therefore, the UPT should recruit additional staff and conduct regular technical skill training and development. The focus should be on improving competencies, work efficiency, and understanding of implemented policies through workshops, technical certifications, and digital-based training.

Similarly, Van Meter and Van Horn [18] argue that adequate resources including funding, labor, facilities, and technology are critical for policy success. Any mismatch between resources and policy needs will hinder goal attainment. Based on this theory, the UPT should conduct a resource needs analysis before policy implementation to ensure that resource availability aligns with needs. For example, they should develop an effective budget allocation plan that prioritizes essential implementation needs, such as staff training, procurement of facilities, and development of supporting technologies.

Grindle [19] also supports this view, stating that both human and material resources play key roles in policy implementation. According to Grindle, effective implementation depends on the competence and commitment of human resources, as well as

adequate facilities and funding. Therefore, the UPT should take strategic steps to increase the effectiveness of population administration policy implementation. These steps include providing staff training to enhance technical, administrative, and public service skills; ensuring the availability of supporting infrastructure such as IT devices and comfortable service spaces; and allocating funds transparently and accountably to support service quality improvement programs.

The findings are also consistent with Pressman and Wildavsky's theory, which posits that successful policy implementation requires the coordination of various resources including time, money, and personnel. Inadequate resources lead to implementation failure. Thus, the UPT should take strategic actions to ensure the availability and coordination of resources for successful implementation. These actions include establishing a clear coordination mechanism among the UPT, the district-level Disdukcapil, and other relevant stakeholders to synchronize resource allocation (time, budget, and manpower). They should also design structured work schedules for each administrative process to reduce waiting times and improve public satisfaction. Moreover, they should optimize budget usage by ensuring that each expenditure directly contributes to improving service quality, such as through procurement of tools or systems that speed up administrative processes.

By implementing these steps, the UPT of the Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency, can ensure that population administration policies are executed as planned, using personnel, infrastructure, and funds optimally. With proper management of human resources, work facilities, and budgets, operational efficiency can be achieved without resource wastage. These actions will enable the creation of better administrative services and support the successful, sustainable implementation of population administration policies.

C. Disposition

This study found that dispositional support for the implementation of population administration policy at the Integrated Service Unit (UPT) of the Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency is already well-established. This is evidenced by the high commitment of staff in implementing the policy, their positive attitudes and perceptions toward the policy, and the presence of coordination and collaboration among staff in supporting the implementation. These findings can be directly linked to Edward III's Policy Implementation Theory [15], which states that disposition, or the attitude of implementers, is one of the key factors determining policy implementation success. According to Edward III, disposition includes the commitment, attitude, and perception of policy implementers toward the policy being carried out. When implementers have a positive disposition, policy implementation is more likely to be effective.

Commitment

The findings reveal a strong commitment from UPT staff in carrying out population administration policies. Edward III emphasizes that implementers' commitment is crucial because it determines the seriousness of policy execution. According to the researchers, this strong commitment reflects a high sense of dedication and responsibility among staff in supporting the implementation of policies, which facilitates the achievement of policy objectives.

Positive Attitudes and Perceptions

The findings show that staff have positive attitudes and favorable perceptions toward the population administration policy. According to Edward III, positive attitudes among policy implementers influence how they carry out their tasks. If the implementers' attitudes or perceptions are negative, the policy is less likely to be implemented effectively. The researchers argue that these positive attitudes indicate a good understanding of the policy's importance and a conscious effort to serve the public optimally.

Coordination and Teamwork

The study also highlights the presence of coordination and teamwork among UPT staff in supporting policy implementation. Coordination and collaboration are part of a strong organizational disposition. Edward III notes that positive disposition also includes the ability to work collaboratively to achieve policy goals. According to the researchers, good teamwork among staff reflects organizational synergy, supporting effective implementation and minimizing internal obstacles within the UPT.

Summary of Dispositional Support

The findings confirm that the disposition of UPT staff—reflected in their commitment, positive attitudes and perceptions, and collaboration—has contributed significantly to effective implementation of population administration policy. With strong dispositional support, policy execution becomes more efficient and aligned with expected outcomes. This supports the importance of disposition as outlined in Edward III's theory.

Theoretical Alignment and Strategic Recommendations

These findings are consistent with the theory of Mazmanian and Sabatier [17], which asserts that the disposition of implementers influences how they interpret and implement policy. Implementers who understand and strongly support a policy are more effective in overcoming implementation barriers. The researchers recommend that the UPT take strategic steps to ensure implementers' disposition supports successful implementation. These include fostering a high sense of responsibility and commitment through motivation, recognition for good performance, and creating a collaborative work culture. Additionally, providing opportunities for implementers to give feedback on policy execution will strengthen their involvement and support. A supportive work environment with adequate facilities also contributes to optimal performance.

The findings also align with Van Meter and Van Horn [18], who assert that implementers' attitudes, commitment, and understanding of policy goals are critical to successful implementation. The researchers suggest that the UPT take strategic actions to cultivate and reinforce positive attitudes and commitment. These may include internal meetings to explain the policy's goals, benefits, and impact on society, instilling values of discipline, responsibility, and professionalism, and conducting regular evaluations of attitudes, motivation, and policy understanding. Challenges identified during evaluations should be promptly addressed.

According to Grindle [19], disposition plays a vital role in policy implementation. It includes implementers' commitment, attitudes, and motivation. Misalignment between implementers' disposition and policy goals can create obstacles. The researchers recommend that the UPT take strategic actions to ensure alignment, such as encouraging UPT leadership to model positive behavior and foster a service-oriented work culture. Strong and inspirational leadership promotes similar attitudes among staff. Additionally, providing financial and non-financial incentives to those who show positive attitudes and performance can boost motivation and support effective implementation.

Lastly, the findings are in line with the theory of Pressman and Wildavsky, which stresses that the success of policy implementation is heavily influenced by implementers' attitudes and commitment. Inconsistent attitudes and lack of support from implementers may lead to policy failure. The researchers advise that the UPT implement strategic steps to ensure supportive attitudes and strong commitment. These include instilling a strong work ethic through mentoring, guidance, and clear delegation of responsibilities. Training programs should address not only technical skills but also mental preparedness, professional attitude, and understanding of policy intent.

Through these measures, implementers at the UPT of the Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict will have a strong understanding, robust support, and high commitment toward policy implementation. This will foster positive attitudes, strengthen implementers' commitment, and ensure policy goals are achieved effectively, resulting in improved public service delivery. Such efforts will enhance implementation effectiveness and reduce barriers throughout the policy execution process.

D. Bureaucratic Structure

This study found that bureaucratic structure support for the implementation of population administration policy at the Integrated Service Unit (UPT) of the Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency is well established. This is evidenced by the clear division of tasks and authority in line with an organizational structure that supports policy implementation, the application of standard operating procedures (SOPs) in executing the policy, and the presence of internal monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to ensure compliance with regulations. These findings align with Edward III's Policy Implementation Theory [15], which asserts that bureaucratic structure is a key factor for successful policy implementation. According to Edward III, bureaucratic structure includes a clear division of tasks and authority, established operating procedures, and oversight during policy execution. A sound bureaucratic structure enables policies to be implemented systematically, efficiently, and in alignment with intended goals.

Task Division and Authority

The research shows that tasks and responsibilities are allocated according to an organizational structure that supports effective policy execution. Edward III emphasizes that a clear organizational structure ensures that each individual or unit understands their role and responsibilities in the implementation process, preventing overlap and facilitating coordination. The researchers argue that with proper task and authority distribution, staff can work within their capacity, making policy implementation more effective.

Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs)

The findings show that SOPs are applied in executing population administration policy. Edward III stresses the importance of structured procedures to ensure consistent and rule-compliant implementation. SOPs serve as technical guidelines to ensure services

and policy execution are effective and efficient. The presence of SOPs indicates that the policy implementation process follows clear operational standards, enabling staff to work in a more directed and transparent manner.

Internal Supervision and Evaluation

The study also found that internal supervision and evaluation mechanisms exist at the UPT to ensure policies are implemented properly. According to Edward III, supervision and evaluation are essential components of bureaucratic structure that enhance the effectiveness of policy implementation. The researchers note that monitoring ensures that every implementation phase follows the prescribed procedures, while evaluation allows for the identification of problems and continuous improvement.

Summary of Bureaucratic Structure Support

This research confirms that bureaucratic structure—as a key factor in Edward III's theory—has been functioning effectively at the UPT. This is reflected through: (1) clear division of roles and authority that ensures work efficiency and coordination, (2) application of SOPs that serve as operational guides for consistent policy implementation, and (3) internal monitoring and evaluation mechanisms that ensure compliance and adaptive improvements. With a robust bureaucratic structure, the implementation of population administration policy becomes more effective, efficient, and results-oriented, as described by Edward III.

Theoretical Support and Strategic Recommendations

These findings align with Lipsky's theory [20], which argues that successful policy implementation depends heavily on bureaucratic structure at the street level—where administrative personnel interact directly with the public. Poor structure hinders service delivery. Therefore, the researchers recommend that the UPT take steps to enhance the operational-level bureaucratic structure. This includes: simplifying and streamlining work procedures to reduce unnecessary bureaucratic barriers and granting field officers limited autonomy to make quick operational decisions.

The findings also support Van Meter and Van Horn's theory [18], which highlights the importance of organizational and bureaucratic structures in policy success. A sound structure facilitates coordination among implementing units, monitoring, and execution. The researchers suggest strategic steps such as restructuring the UPT organization to make it clearer and more flexible, with well-defined roles and responsibilities. They also recommend establishing regular coordination mechanisms and developing transparent monitoring systems to detect and address problems early.

According to Wantu [21], the effectiveness of policy implementation is strongly influenced by the legislative process at the local parliamentary level (DPRD). In the context of Bunta's UPT, population administration policy should be based on regional regulations that are adaptive, responsive, and aligned with local needs. Without synergy between legislators and technical implementers, policy risks remaining a mere formal document with limited practical impact.

These findings are also consistent with Grindle's theory [19], which argues that an efficient bureaucratic structure is crucial for policy implementation. A supportive structure facilitates information flow, supervision, and effective coordination. The researchers recommend strategic actions such as: restructuring the organization with clear task and role delineation, strengthening internal coordination through regular meetings, forming coordination teams, and establishing clear communication pathways. They also suggest implementing real-time monitoring systems (digital or manual) for performance tracking and evaluation.

Pressman and Wildavsky's theory further supports these findings, noting that overly complex bureaucratic structures can obstruct policy implementation. Flexible and efficient structures promote effective communication and coordination. The researchers advocate for simplifying the UPT's structure to accelerate decision-making and execution. This includes reducing unnecessary administrative procedures, adopting an adaptive structure where roles adjust to situational demands, and ensuring leadership is capable of fostering collaboration and proactively addressing barriers.

By implementing these strategies, the UPT of the Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict can improve its bureaucratic structure at the operational level, thereby enhancing the effectiveness, efficiency, and responsiveness of population administration services. A strong structure will facilitate inter-unit coordination, ease monitoring, and support optimal policy implementation. The ultimate result is improved public service delivery. With these steps, the UPT is expected to build an efficient bureaucratic structure that ensures smooth information flow, supervision, and policy coordination—positively impacting policy success and service quality.

These findings are in line with those of Aneta & Tohopi [22], who emphasize that local-level policy implementation, such as at the UPT, depends on communication strength, resource availability, and implementer attitudes. Optimal population administration services require a well-defined bureaucratic structure and effective vertical and horizontal communication. Without these elements,

policies remain abstract instructions, difficult to translate into real service. Similarly, Abdussamad & Amala [23] stress that effective public service policy implementation requires strong internal strategies, particularly in human resource development, regular evaluation, IT utilization, and leadership commitment. In Bunta's UPT, such strategies form the foundation for effective, efficient, and responsive population administration services.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research findings and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The communication or socialization process of the policy in the implementation of population administration at the Integrated Service Unit (UPT) of the Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency has not been optimal, resulting in low public awareness of the importance of civil registration documents and vital records.
2. Resource support for policy implementation still faces various challenges and limitations, including human resources, facilities and infrastructure, and budget constraints, which hinder the optimal execution of the policy.
3. Dispositional support from implementers at the UPT is strong, with high commitment and positive attitudes toward policy implementation.
4. Bureaucratic structure support is well established, with a clear division of tasks and authority aligned with the organizational structure that supports the implementation of population administration policy, along with the application of standard operating procedures (SOPs) in policy execution.

SUGGESTION

The following are the recommendations derived from this research:

1. Improve Underperforming Aspects and Maintain Existing Strengths. Aspects that have not yet performed optimally need to be improved, while those that are already functioning well should be maintained and continuously refined. Communication remains a critical weakness that must be addressed immediately. Strategies include using simple language, involving local community leaders, and selecting media that are familiar and accessible to the public. Socialization activities must be conducted directly, intensively, consistently, and on a continuous basis.
2. Enhance Three Key Aspects to Optimize Policy Implementation. Policy implementation will be more effective if three main aspects are improved: First, enhancing staff capacity through education and training. Second, providing and maintaining supporting facilities and infrastructure. Third, allocating adequate budget to support population administration services at the UPT Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency.
3. Foster Implementers' Commitment and Responsibility. The leadership of the UPT should encourage responsibility and commitment among implementers by offering motivation and recognition for good performance. A collaborative work culture should be continuously developed. Values such as discipline, responsibility, and professionalism should be instilled through ongoing coaching to ensure implementers exhibit positive and consistent work attitudes.
4. Simplify Procedures and Strengthen Organizational Structure. Work procedures need to be reorganized to be simpler and more efficient, enabling staff to carry out their duties more easily and reducing unnecessary bureaucratic obstacles. The organizational structure of the UPT also needs to be revised to be clearer and more flexible. Task and responsibility assignments should be well-defined to support an effective workflow.

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Cite this Article: Putri, S.N., Wantu, S.M., Mozin, S.Y. (2025). Implementation of Population Administration Policy at the Integrated Service Unit (UPT) of the Population and Civil Registration Office in Bunta Subdistrict, Banggai Regency. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 8(5), pp. 2392-2403. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i5-50>